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 Creation: 2/25/2025 12:14:56 PM
 Sample Name: Proszki

Si

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 32.74 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	30.7	0.10	49.9	10.1
O K	3.6	0.04	4.4	7.6
Si K	65.7	0.07	45.7	5.6

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/Si/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.6 Live Time(s): 299.8 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

Det: Element-C2B